

COCOPREND

Code of Conduct for Preclinical Neuroimaging data

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- Large volumes of data are generated in **preclinical neuroimaging** research
- Researchers need support to make it **FAIR** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
- Good research management maximizes **utility** of animal experiments
- A fragment landscape of resources makes it **hard to get started**

COCOPREND **compiles** and **distills** resources to facilitate responsible and ethical use, sharing and management of preclinical (animal) neuroimaging data.

Concepts	Metadata	Sharing & Publishing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 3R Principles ❖ Reproducibility ❖ Open Research Data ❖ Preregistration ❖ FAIR Principles ❖ Data Management Plans ❖ Legal & Ethical 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Standards ❖ Documentation & protocols ❖ Tables & Spreadsheets ❖ Metadata files ❖ Controlled vocabularies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ File formats ❖ Version controls ❖ Archives ❖ Online Repositories

Available in:

Website <https://crsuzh.pages.uzh.ch/cocoprend/>

Keep it alive!

Search through all contents

Access the repository with the source files (Markdown)

Download as PDF

Chapter list

Chapter contents

COCOPREND feeds on ...

- ❖ sharing good practices
- ❖ up-to-date links
- ❖ useful tools
- ❖ researchers
- ❖ community efforts

Technical notes

- ❖ Source files are plain-text **Markdown**
- ❖ Stored in a **Git** repository (version controlled)
- ❖ Saved as PDF & HTML with **QUARTO**
- ❖ Gitlab pages host the website (for free)
- ❖ Website automatically updated if source files are edited
- ❖ Maintainers can edit from the internet browser
- ❖ Maintainers do not need advanced programming
- ❖ All code & files freely accessible at:
<https://crsuzh.pages.uzh.ch/cocoprend/>
- ❖ First release awaiting publication (DOI)
- ❖ Similar workflow reported in detailed in [1]

REFERENCES

[1] Fraga González, G., et al. "Where Are My Data? the AFFORD Workflow to Create Your Own Data Index with Git, R and Quarto." MetaArXiv, 2024. https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/64fch_v1

The project COCOPREND is funded by Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences 01.10.2024 - 30.06.2025

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